

Activated triply periodic minimal surfaces (TPMS) gyroid supports for efficient ammonia synthesis in membrane-integrated reactors

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ABSTRACT

Ammonia is an essential chemical widely used in industry, with its production dominated by the highly energy-intensive Haber-Bosch process. Membrane reactor technology offers a promising alternative by integrating reaction and selective product separation, thereby enabling higher process efficiencies and milder operating conditions. In this work, we investigate a new membrane reactor composed of a carbon membrane immersed in an Activated Triply Periodic Minimal Surface (TPMS) gyroid support uniformly coated with a Ru-based catalytic layer. Different operating conditions have been investigated; The most favourable baseline conditions were identified at the lowest WHSV ($715 \text{ mLn g}_{\text{cat}}^{-1} \text{ h}^{-1}$), and with an under-stoichiometric $\text{H}_2:\text{N}_2$ feed ratio of 2:1, reflecting both the proximity to thermodynamic equilibrium and the beneficial impact of reduced hydrogen partial pressure on Ru-based catalysis.

At 250 °C and 40 bar, increasing the sweep gas to feed flow ratio (SW) to 10 led NH_3 production rate enhancements of approximately 43 % and corresponding NH_3 yield gains of 15 %, with an NH_3 recovery factor of 84 %. At lower pressure (30 bar) and higher temperatures (350–450 °C), the membrane reactor still enhanced NH_3 production rate at reduced sweep ratios, with gains of about 1–20 % at SW = 1 and 17–41 % at SW = 4 relative to the SCR. However, the NH_3 recovery factor dropped to 64–70 % for SW = 1 and 41–66 % for SW of 4, compared with 87–95 % at 40 bar. This behaviour indicates a clear trade-off between productivity and product recovery as pressure and sweep ratio are adjusted. At 450 °C and 10–40 bar, with a SW = 4, H_2 conversion exceeded the equilibrium value by approximately 15–30 %, and the conversion achieved at 400 °C in the SCR was already attained at 300 °C in the SCMR. At 400 °C and 40 bar with SW = 4, H_2 conversion, NH_3 production rate, and NH_3 yield increased by 83.4 %, 76.9 %, and 53.4 %, respectively, compared to the structured reactor. Overall, these results provide a clear proof of concept for the application of structured membrane reactors to ammonia synthesis, demonstrating that an appropriate combination of structured Ru-based catalysts and carbon membrane integration can deliver enhanced efficiency and equilibrium shifting under milder operating conditions, and offering a solid basis for future scale-up and process optimization studies.

1. Introduction

Ammonia holds promise as a potential green energy carrier and could be a fuel solution for clean power generation, particularly for long-distance transportation [1]. Among fuel-use options, ammonia cracking stands out as the cleanest approach. The process first decomposes ammonia into hydrogen and nitrogen. When that hydrogen burns (with nitrogen acting as inert), it produces only water vapor and nitrogen,

with no carbon emissions. This makes it a viable fossil fuel replacement when using green ammonia from renewables. [2]. Moreover NH_3 has a high hydrogen content (17.8w %) and can be liquefied at a reasonable temperature (-33.34 °C) at atmospheric pressure [3]. One of the main advantage is the existing global ammonia infrastructure. In 2024, around 45 million tons (MT) of ammonia (22% of production) was transported via various modalities, domestically and internationally [4]. While ammonia offers many industrial benefits, 96% of it is still

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produced via the conventional Haber–Bosch process, which relies on fossil fuels both as feedstock and as an energy source for hydrogen generation. As a result, the majority of associated greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions originate from the fossil-based hydrogen production step % [5].

The Haber-Bosch process is a well-developed ammonia synthesis technology. The process converts N_2 from atmosphere into NH_3 through the reaction with H_2 [6]. Conventional ammonia synthesis catalysts for the Haber-Bosch process fall mainly into two categories: fused iron and supported metallic catalysts [7]. In the triply promoted (Al, Ca and K) traditional magnetite (Fe_3O_4) catalysts (fused iron), aluminium and calcium oxides are the structural promoters and potassium oxide is the electronic promoter [8]. The mixed catalyst is proved to be so effective that even now all ammonia catalysts in the world are still manufactured based on this principle [9], exhibiting high activity with an ammonia conversion of 15–20% at the converter outlet achieved for space velocities of 30 000–10 000 h^{-1} at 425 °C and 150 bar [10]. These multi promoted iron (Fe) catalysts are highly optimized for stability and large-scale operation, though they require severe reaction conditions [11]. Greater energy savings could be obtained by an improvement in catalytic activity that would allow for operation at lower temperatures and lower pressures [12]. Ruthenium is a possible catalyst for ammonia synthesis because of its higher activity at low pressure and temperature compared to that of iron-based catalysts [13]. However, it is still not clear whether the significantly higher cost and shorter life-time is justified by the higher activity compared to traditional iron-based catalysts [14]. Another obstacle for industrial ammonia synthesis with Ru-loaded catalysts is hydrogen poisoning under high hydrogen pressures [15]. To make use of the Ru metal affordably and sustainably, the key challenge is to develop highly efficient Ru-based catalysts with excellent stability for both fundamental study and industrial application [16]. Current research aims to improve active site exposure and suppress hydrogen poisoning by employing tailored supports and promoters [17]. Examples include Cs-doped Ru/ZrO₂ [18], Ru/CeO₂-Al₂O₃ [19], Ru/CeO₂-La₂O₃-SiO₂ [20], Ru/Ce-N/C [21].

Conventional packed-bed reactors (PBRs) are inherently constrained by heat and mass transfer limitations. These mass transfer resistances reduce effective catalyst utilization and, in membrane reactors, hinder hydrogen transport from the active sites in the catalyst bed to the membrane surface [22]. To overcome these constraints, structured catalysts and reactors have emerged as a promising strategy for process intensification, attracting growing interest within the chemical engineering community and industry alike. From the point of view of applicability for on-site production, it is convenient to have the catalyst in the form of structured reactor [23]. The metal-structured catalysts have a large ratio of the geometric reaction surface area to the reaction volume (S/V) and higher heat transfer rate per unit volume of process flow (US/V) [24]. Among the various supports investigated, open-cell foams and monolithic structures have gained increasing use in processes that demand high gas throughput, low pressure drop, and enhanced transport properties [25], [26], [27], [28]. A structured support is typically defined as a continuous metallic or ceramic matrix containing a network of channels or pores, onto which catalytically active phases are dispersed [29]. These active materials can be incorporated directly into the matrix or more commonly deposited by coating techniques, with the latter being preferred due to its versatility and ease of implementation [30]. In recent years, the development of cellular metallic structures known as Periodic Open Cellular Structures (POCS) has opened new perspectives for catalyst design [31], [26], [32]. These architectures, enabled by advances in additive manufacturing (AM) or three-dimensional (3D) printing, are generated by repeating unit cells such as cubic, tetrahedral, or diamond throughout space to create highly regular frameworks [33]. POCS combine the beneficial features of open-cell foams and honeycomb monoliths, including enhanced radial mass and heat transport, improved tortuosity, reduced pressure drop, and tuneable porosity [34]. A particularly intriguing class of these

geometries are Triply Periodic Minimal Surfaces (TPMS), which are mathematically defined as structures characterized by zero mean curvature and continuous three-dimensional periodicity, namely gyroid, Schwarz diamond, and primitive structures [35]. TPMS offer unique advantages for catalytic applications: they provide interconnected pathways with high specific surface area, controllable pore size distribution, and superior mechanical stability due to efficient stress distribution [36]. Beyond catalysis, TPMS lattices are being explored in areas such as lightweight structural components, heat exchangers, energy storage devices, and biomimetic systems, owing to their ability to simultaneously optimize fluid transport, heat dissipation, and mechanical strength [37], [38]. Their intrinsic self-supporting architecture makes them particularly suitable for additive manufacturing, which enables precise tailoring of geometrical features at multiple length scales [39]. Overall, the integration of POCS and TPMS architectures into catalytic reactor design represents a frontier in process intensification, with the potential to overcome longstanding limitations of traditional reactor technologies and open pathways toward highly efficient, multifunctional catalytic systems.

Recent work have shown also the possibility of integrating this periodic structure in membrane reactor [40]. This technology represents a promising alternative to conventional H–B systems by enabling NH_3 synthesis under less severe conditions. By selectively removing specific reactants or products, the membrane improves reaction efficiency, drives the equilibrium toward higher conversion, and reduces the need for downstream separation. Moreover, combining reaction and separation in a single unit intensifies the process, which can lower capital requirements and enable modular, scalable designs suitable for decentralized NH_3 production [41]. Current research is increasingly exploring carbon molecular sieve (CMS) membranes as a cost-effective alternative, owing to their high thermal stability and physical-chemical stability as well as their excellent mechanical strength. Under appropriate thicknesses, CMS membranes can withstand large pressure differentials, and therefore operate as an energy-efficient gas separation technology [42], [43], [44]. In addition, numerous studies have focused on the development of metal-doped CMS membranes to further tune pore structure and separation performance [45], [46], [47], [48]. NH_3 has one lone pair of electrons that can be donated to metal cations, forming coordinate covalent bonds that are significantly stronger than hydrogen bonds. In this work, Cu^{2+} cations were incorporated into the Novolac phenolic resin precursor solution prior to membrane fabrication, enabling the preparation of a Cu-modified CMS membrane designed to alter both the pore structure and the specific interactions between the membrane and ammonia.

The focus of this work is to experimentally investigate, for the first time, the performance of a membrane reactor system for ammonia synthesis, in which a structured gyroid-based catalyst is combined with a copper carbon molecular sieve (Cu-CMS) membrane. The gyroid structures were washcoated with a developmental Ru-based catalyst. The gyroid architecture was characterized by a cell size of 5 mm, a sheet diameter of 0.34 mm, and an overall porosity of 70 %, offering high surface area, interconnected flow paths, and robust mechanical stability. This tailored design enables a close integration of the catalytic structure with the CMS membrane, ensuring both efficient catalytic activity and selective product separation within a single intensified reactor system. The membrane reactor was tested under different conditions to investigate the effect of temperature, pressure, feed composition, weight hourly space velocity (WHSV) and sweep gas to feed flow ratio (SW).

2. Experimental

2.1. Materials and preparation

2.1.1. TPMS gyroid supports: manufacturing and catalytic activation by dip/spin coating

The Ni-alloy (IN625) Gyroid supports were manufactured using the

Laser Powder Bed (LPBF) Fusion technique based on CAD files, resulting in cylindrical structures with a diameter of 26.66 mm and a length of 100 mm. The supports, incorporating a central channel ($\varnothing = 15.1$ mm), are specifically designed to host a CMS membrane. The gyroid architecture was characterized by a cell size of 5 mm, a sheet diameter of 0.34 mm, a specific surface area of 4.3 mm^{-2} , a pore size diameter of 2.16 mm and an overall porosity of 70%. In Fig. 1 rendering of the support investigated in this work is reported, associated to its relative single cell unit.

A developmental Ru-based (2.5 wt %) catalyst provided by Johnson Matthey (JM) in powder shape, was used to prepare a slurry mixture for activating the two identical Gyroid supports. The composition of the prepared slurry is reported in Table 1. The powder dispersions were prepared following a procedure described elsewhere [49].

The dispersion medium was prepared by dissolving polyvinyl alcohol (PVA, 87-89 % hydrolysed, Sigma-Aldrich) in distilled water, followed by the addition of glycerol (GLY, 99.5 % bi-distilled, Analar Normapur®) under magnetic stirring at $85 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. In this formulation, glycerol served as a dispersant, polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) as a rheology modifier, and distilled water as a solvent/diluent. The catalyst powder was subsequently incorporated into the dispersion medium, and the resulting slurry was homogenized by ball milling (Planetary Ball Mill BM40-POWTEQ) with zirconia spheres (1 cm diameter, mass ratio of spheres to catalyst powder = 7:1) for 24 h at 300 rpm in a 250 cm^3 zirconia jar. Before being added to the dispersion, the catalyst powder itself was pre-milled in the same jar for 3 h at 300 rpm. After the milling process, the slurry underwent a 30 min sonication treatment to minimize foaming. Rheological characterization (Fig. 2) revealed that the slurry exhibited Newtonian behaviour. This property is particularly advantageous for coating applications, as it ensures the slurry maintains a stable viscosity across varying shear rates, allowing for predictable flow and easy application. As a result, uniform and defect-free coatings can be achieved, with the slurry readily penetrating small pores and conforming to the complex geometries of the support structure.

Slurry deposition was carried out using a combined dip-spin coating procedure previously optimized [50]. Prior to deposition, the as-built gyroid supports were cleaned by ultrasonic treatment in an acetone/water solution (50:50 vol %) for 30 min, thoroughly rinsed with water, and dried at $120 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 1 h. The structures were then calcined in air at $900 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 6 h. To ensure complete wetting of the porous network, samples were immersed in the slurry for about 10 s. Excess slurry was subsequently removed with a commercial spin-coater (Laurell WS-650Mz-23 NPPB) operated at 1000 rpm, with 20 s rotation time and an acceleration of 1000 rpm s^{-2} . After each coating step, samples were

Table 1
Composition of the prepared slurry.

Catalyst (g)	Powder catalyst (%)	Glycerol (%)	PVA (%)	Water (%)	Slurry volume (mL)	Catalyst loaded (g)
2.5 wt % Ru-based 35	22.4	42.50	1.50	33.60	155	Pc.1 = 6.54 Pc.2 = 6.15

Fig. 2. Slurry rheological behaviour.

flash dried in air at $350 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 6 min. This process was repeated approximately 11 times to reach a washcoat load of $\approx 6 \text{ g cm}^{-3}$, as reported in Table 1. The structures were then calcined at $500 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 6 h (heating rate: $5 \text{ }^\circ\text{C min}^{-1}$). Gravimetric analysis was performed after each drying and calcination step to monitor weight evolution and confirm washcoat loading. Fig. 3 shows image of the two activated Gyroid supports used in this study, compared with the bare one.

2.1.2. Carbon molecular sieve (CMS) membrane fabrication

Carbon Molecular Sieve (CMS) membranes are the product of heat treatment of thermosetting polymers under non-oxidizing environment [51]. Novolac resin was synthesized by the acid-catalysed phenol-formaldehyde condensation as reported in Ref. [52] using phenol (99 %) and formaldehyde (37 %). A solution containing Novolac resin (16 wt %), formaldehyde (2.4 wt %) and ethylenediamine (0.4 wt %) dispersed in *N*-Methyl-2-pyrrolidone (NMP) as a solvent, was prepared and heated at $90 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 90 min to form a Novolac oligomer. After

Fig. 1. Rendering of Gyroid structure ($L =$ Length, \varnothing^{ex} External diameter, \varnothing^{h} hole diameter) and relative unit cell; d_c represents the cell dimension, d_s the thickness of the sheet and P_s the pore size dimension.

Fig. 3. Images of bare (central) and coated Gyroid support (left and right).

cooling, an appropriate amount of an aqueous $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ solution (10 wt % of Cu^{+2}) was added to obtain 0.1 wt % of Cu^{+2} in the dipping solution. A 50 cm long asymmetric porous $\alpha\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ tubes ($\text{O}^{\text{in}} = 7$ mm, $\text{O}^{\text{ex}} = 10$ mm), with 100 nm average pore size on the external surface was immersed in the dipping solution for 90 s. The coated support was placed vertically in an oven at 90°C for 12 h to complete polymerization solvent removal. Finally, the membrane was carbonized at 550°C for 2 h under N_2 atmosphere.

The membrane was cut so that its overall length slightly exceeded that of the TPMS Gyroid-based catalyst. It was then sealed at both ends using Swagelok connections with graphite rings to reduce mechanical stress. One end was closed with a dead-end Swagelok connection, while the other remained open to allow connection to the flange, as shown in Fig. 4.

2.2. Characterizations

2.2.1. TPMS gyroid-based catalyst

A Keyence VHX-7000 digital optical microscope characterized by a fully integrated head using stage shift technology and 4K mode for high-resolution imaging, was used for morphological measurements. Detailed images of the Gyroid catalyst were acquired with VHX-E20 (High-Resolution, Low-Magnification Objective Lens 20-100 \times) and VHX-E100 lenses (High-Resolution, Medium-Magnification Objective Lens 100-500 \times). Measurements were taken at various points on the struts and cells to identify any discrepancies from the CAD model.

The rheology of the slurry used for the coating of the structured catalyst was characterized using a rotational rheometer (Modular Compact Rheometer MCR 92, Anton Paar GmbH, Graz, Austria). Measurements were performed at 25°C by using a double gap measuring system, and slurry viscosity was measured in the $0.1\text{-}3000\text{ s}^{-1}$ shear rates range.

2.2.2. CMS membrane

The membrane employed in this study was first characterized in

Fig. 4. Carbon Molecular Sieve Membrane sealed using Swagelok fittings to enable connection to the reactor flange.

terms of its permeation performance, using the permeance and selectivity definitions given in Eqs. (1)–(3). Single and mixed gas permeation experiments were carried out in the same setup used for the catalytic tests, but in absence of catalyst, and under identical temperature and pressure conditions. Gas compositions were analyzed using a Compact GC 4.0 micro-gas chromatograph (Global Analyser Solutions, GAS) equipped with two analytical channels and two thermal conductivity detectors (TCDs). The first channel employed a Molsieve 5A column ($7\text{ m} \times 0.32\text{ mm}$) for the separation of N_2 , H_2 , and CH_4 , using Ar as carrier gas at 100°C , with an injection temperature of 130°C and an inlet pressure of 110 kPa. The second channel used an Rtx-Volatile Amine column ($30\text{ m} \times 0.32\text{ mm}$) for NH_3 analysis, with He as carrier gas at 100°C , an injection temperature of 130°C , and an inlet pressure of 75 kPa.

$$\mathcal{P}_i = \frac{\Phi_{v,i}}{V_m A_{mem} (P^R y_i^R - P^P y_i^P)} \quad (1)$$

$$S_{i/j} = \frac{\mathcal{P}_i}{\mathcal{P}_j} \quad (2)$$

$$SF_{i/j} = \frac{y_i^P / y_j^P}{y_i^R / y_j^R} \quad (3)$$

Thermo Scientific™ Phenom Pharos™ G2 Desktop FEG-SEM which is a field-emission scanning electron microscope designed for high-resolution imaging of surfaces and cross-sections, was used to study the morphology of the membrane. It was operated at 10 kV, with magnifications in the range 30 000–35 000 \times , and elemental composition was analyzed by energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX).

2.3. Experimental setup

The configuration of the experimental setup used to perform the tests is shown in Fig. 5. The gas supply system includes nitrogen (N_2), hydrogen (H_2), ammonia (NH_3), and methane (CH_4). Gases are delivered either from high-pressure gas bottle (Linde) located in a gas cabinet equipped with pressure reducers (up to 66 bar for N_2 and H_2 , and up to 8 bar for NH_3 , limited by vapor-liquid equilibrium) or via a centralized feed line (N_2 for Pneumatic Valve Island and CH_4 for internal standard during analysis) operating at 6 bar. Flow rates are controlled by Bronkhorst mass-flow controllers (MFCs) with operating ranges of 20-1000 mLn min^{-1} for N_2 , 40-2000 mLn min^{-1} for H_2 , and 10-500 mLn min^{-1} for NH_3 . Pneumatically actuated Swagelok valves are used to automatically open and close the gas lines, while Swagelok check valves equipped with Kalrez® seals are installed downstream of the MFCs to prevent backflow. The reactor can be bypassed when required through three-way Swagelok valves. The reactor consist of an Inconel vessel ($\text{O}^{\text{ex}} = 33$ mm, $\text{O}^{\text{in}} = 29$ mm, $L = 300$ mm) that accommodates a TPMS unit, into which a CMS membrane is integrated. The assembly comprises two 10 cm TPMS segments stacked vertically, yielding a 20 cm total active length, as shown in Fig. 6. The membrane is sealed to the top flange, resulting in an overall membrane length of approximately 21 cm. To ensure thermal uniformity, the retentate and permeate feed lines, as well as the reactor body, are equipped with electrical heat tracing for pre-heating (IS-SP-H/230V/330W/KE1.5 M). The retentate and permeate streams are physically separated: the retentate leaves the reactor laterally, whereas the permeate is withdrawn from the top flange. To ensure co-current operation, the reaction stream enters from the bottom of the reactor, while the sweep gas is introduced from the top via an internal capillary ($\text{O}^{\text{ext}} = 3$ mm) that extends to the end of the membrane and then flows back along its length in the same axial direction as the retentate stream. Temperature is monitored using digital temperature transmitters: two thermocouples are installed inside the reactor (TE 502, TE 801E), one control thermocouple is positioned externally on the reactor wall (TC 801A), and additional control thermocouples are

Fig. 5. P&ID of the experimental setup used for the Structured Catalyst reactor (SCR)/Structured Catalyst-based Membrane Reactor (SCMR).

Fig. 6. Internal sectional view of the tubular membrane reactor showing the TPMS catalyst support and central CMS membrane.

located at the preheating sections of both the retentate and permeate lines (TC 501, TC 601). A thermocouple (TE 602) is also embedded within the membrane to monitor local conditions along the separation interface. The entire reactor is enclosed within an electrical oven (247 Tailorsteel) to maintain isothermal conditions, and nitrogen is continuously flushed through the oven to ensure an inert atmosphere and prevent corrosion. Analog pressure indicators (PI 100, PI 200, PI 300) are installed on the gas inlet lines, while electronic pressure transmitters (PT 502, PT 602 (Pressure Control Solutions)) are placed at the outlet of both retentate and permeate streams to monitor the actual system

pressure. Back-pressure regulators (BPR-500, BPR-600, Equilibar LF, SS316, 69 bar, 150 °C) are used to regulate pressure separately on the two sides of the membrane. Rupture discs are installed at the outlets of both streams, set to relieve at a maximum pressure of 80 bar \pm 5 % at 20 °C to ensure safe operation. Upon leaving the reactor, gas streams can be directed to a Compact GC 4.0 micro-gas chromatograph (described in Section 1.2.2) for compositional analysis. Methane is used as an internal standard to enable accurate determination of flow rates at both the retentate and permeate outlets. Finally, all exhaust gases are passed through a scrubbing system to remove residual ammonia before being

safely vented.

2.4. Key performance indicators for reactor performance

The performance of both the structured catalyst reactor (SCR) and the Structured Catalyst-based Membrane Reactor (SCMR) is evaluated using a set of key performance indicators (KPIs), several of which have already been introduced and discussed in a previous study (Eqs. (4)–(7)) [53].

$$\% X_{H_2} = \frac{F_{H_2, in}^R - F_{H_2, out}^R - F_{H_2, tm}}{F_{H_2, in}^R - F_{H_2, tm}^*} \times 100 \quad (4)$$

$$F_{H_2, tm} = F_{H_2, out}^P - F_{H_2, in}^P \quad (5)$$

$$F_{H_2, tm}^* = F_{H_2, out}^P - F_{H_2, in}^P \text{ only if } F_{H_2, tm} \leq 0 \text{ cofeeding} \quad (6)$$

$$\% \text{ Recovery factor} = \frac{F_{NH_3}^P}{F_{NH_3}^R + F_{NH_3}^P} \times 100 \quad (7)$$

$$Y_{NH_3} = \frac{F_{NH_3}^R + F_{NH_3}^P}{F_{H_2, in}^R - F_{H_2, tm}^*} \quad (8)$$

$$NH_3 \text{ production rate} = \frac{F_{NH_3}^R + F_{NH_3}^P}{W_{cat}} \quad (9)$$

$$\% \text{ Improvement} = \frac{SCMR - SCR}{SCR} \times 100 \quad (10)$$

Due to the porous nature of the membrane, hydrogen can diffuse from the reaction zone to the permeate side under normal operating conditions. This *trans*-membrane flux is considered positive when directed outward from the reaction zone and represents a loss of hydrogen available for reaction. Accordingly, the quantity of hydrogen that permeates through the membrane must be deducted from the total amount present in the retentate ($F_{H_2, tm}$). Conversely, when the hydrogen partial pressure on the permeate side surpasses that in the reaction zone,

a reverse transport, known as cofeeding ($F_{H_2, tm}^*$), can occur. This process causes hydrogen to diffuse back into the retentate, effectively enriching the reaction mixture and increasing the amount of reactant available for conversion. The ammonia recovery (% *Recovery factor*) quantifies the fraction of the total ammonia produced that can be collected on the permeate side. The ammonia yield (Y_{NH_3}) expresses the amount of ammonia formed with respect to the hydrogen available in the retentate, considering any cofed hydrogen if applicable. The ammonia production rate (NH_3 *production rate*) considers the total ammonia formed within the system, normalized to the total catalyst used during the experiments, thus providing a consistent basis for productivity comparison. Finally, the percentage improvement quantifies the relative enhancement in performance achieved by the membrane-assisted configuration compared to the conventional reactor system.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. TPMS gyroid-based catalyst: morphological characterization

Fig. 7 shows different optical images of the TPMS Gyroid structures. Sheet diameters and cell sizes of the as-built, uncoated gyroid were measured using the dedicated software of the Keyence VHX-7000 microscope. Thanks to the high reproducibility of the adopted manufacturing technique, only minor variations in sheet dimensions were detected compared to the CAD model (Fig. 1). Measurements performed on the as-built sample (Fig. 7 (a)) confirmed the high resolution of the process, with deviations remaining within narrow tolerances and thus demonstrating the reliability of the fabrication method in accurately reproducing the designed geometry.

The coating process resulted in a uniform catalytic layer, with the porous network fully covered while preserving the open-cell architecture and preventing clogging. Representative images (Fig. 7(b–d)) highlight the homogeneous distribution of the catalyst throughout the gyroid geometry. The spin-coating step was particularly critical in ensuring proper slurry distribution: at higher spinning speeds, excess slurry was effectively removed, leading to thinner layers and preventing pore occlusion.

Fig. 7. Optical images of: a) external surface of the Gyroid support as built; b) external surface of coated Gyroid support; c) view of the activated internal hole zone; d) magnification of the external coated surface.

3.2. CMS membrane: separation performance and morphological characterization

Single and mixed gas permeation experiments were carried out to discriminate the intrinsic behaviour of the membrane and assess how closely it approaches the targeted performance. All measurements were performed in the setup described in Section 1.3, over the full temperature range applied in the reaction tests and at pressures up to 40 bar. The results reported in Fig. 8 refer to a pressure of 8 bar, which corresponds to the maximum attainable ammonia pressure imposed by the equilibrium conditions in the gas cylinder; data at other pressures for hydrogen and nitrogen are provided in the Supplementary Material. Across the full pressure range (Figure S.2-S.6 (a)), nitrogen permeance in single gas tests remained essentially constant at each temperature, indicating negligible pressure dependence and thus the absence of large defects or cracks and of Poiseuille-type flow. In contrast, hydrogen permeance is much higher and increases moderately with temperature from 250 to 450 °C, following an Arrhenius-type trend where $P_{H_2} \propto \exp(-E_{A,H_2}/RT)$; this reflects thermally activated diffusion in ultramicropores with a relatively high diffusion activation energy for H₂ in a molecular-sieving regime. Moreover, the dependence on pressure is weak at lower temperatures (Figures S.2-S.6 (a)), but becomes more pronounced at higher temperatures (400-450 °C). This behaviour can be attributed to the weakening of adsorption effects and the increasing dominance of diffusion through ultramicropores as the rate-controlling step, making hydrogen permeance more sensitive to pressure variations. At very high pressures (30-40 bar), the permeance becomes so high that it could not be accurately measured due to limitations in reactor pressurization (Figure S.6). For ammonia, the dependence on pressure is relatively weak over the investigated range, while permeance is predominantly governed by temperature (Fig. 8 (a)) and decreases markedly as the temperature increases, indicating adsorption-diffusion controlled transport with an apparent Arrhenius activation energy dominated by the loss of NH₃ adsorption sites at elevated temperature. Since the measured ideal selectivities (Fig. 8 (b)) exceed the corresponding Knudsen values ($S_{NH_3/H_2} = 0.34$, $S_{H_2/N_2} = 2.88$), gas transport

mechanism is far from the Knudsen regime and dominated by the membrane pore structure and adsorption effects. As a matter of fact, H₂/N₂ selectivity increases with temperature, consistent with a molecular sieving-dominated mechanism, whereas for NH₃/H₂ it decreases with temperature, reflects the loss of adsorption-enhanced NH₃ transport relative to Arrhenius-type, diffusion-dominated H₂ transport. At the highest temperatures, the ideal selectivities move closer to the Knudsen ratios, suggesting an approach towards a more Knudsen-like regime in which size-independent, collision-controlled transport partially replaces adsorption-dominated diffusion. In addition to single gas measurements, mixed gas permeation tests were conducted using a H₂:N₂ = 1.5:1 feed and a simulated 40 % conversion, resulting in a gas composition of 38 vol % N₂, 42 vol % H₂, and 20 vol % NH₃, chosen to closely resemble the reaction environment. Mixed gas tests at different pressures, shown in Fig. 8 (c) - Figure S. 7-8 (a) reveal stronger competition between hydrogen, nitrogen and ammonia, leading to a reduction of the overall H₂/N₂ separation factor compared to the ideal single gas selectivity. Moreover, the overall permeance of hydrogen and ammonia are lower than the single gas tests, indicating that competitive adsorption of NH₃ partially blocks micropores available to H₂. As temperature rises, NH₃ desorbs and H₂ transport becomes more diffusion-controlled. SEM-EDX analysis, shown in Fig. 9, further confirmed the structural integrity of the selective layer, revealing a continuous ~800 nm thick film without defects and a homogeneous Cu distribution throughout the carbon matrix, as shown in Table S.1.

3.3. Catalytic activity tests

The structured catalyst is evaluated under a range of operating conditions to quantify temperature, pressure, composition, and productivity profiles. To enable a direct comparison with the Structured Catalyst-based Membrane Reactor (SCMR), all catalytic activity tests are performed using the same reactor configuration described in Section 1.3. In this configuration, a ceramic glass tube is inserted inside the structured catalyst in place of the CMS membrane in order to isolate the permeate side while suppressing permeation. Before testing, the

Fig. 8. Membrane performance at different temperatures and $P = 8$ bar: (a) single gas permeance, (b) ideal selectivity, (c) mixed gas permeance, (d) separation factor.

Fig. 9. Cross section SEM-EDX images of the CMSM showing layer thickness and Cu distribution.

structured catalyst is reduced in situ using a 75 % H₂/25 % N₂ mixture, applying successive temperature steps from 200 °C to 550 °C. Subsequently, activity measurements are carried out in the temperature range 250–450 °C, at pressures between 10 and 40 bar, and with inlet molar feed ratios H₂:N₂ = 3:1/2:1. The weight hourly space velocity (WHSV) is varied between 715 and 14 273 mLn g_{cat}⁻¹ h⁻¹ to investigate the influence of contact time on reactor performance.

3.3.1. Effect of the temperatures and pressures

Temperature and pressure are the primary operating variables governing ammonia synthesis, because the reaction is simultaneously limited by kinetics and thermodynamics. As expected from Arrhenius behaviour, Fig. 9 shows the ammonia formation rate which increases with temperature due to faster surface reaction kinetics, up to the point where the equilibrium ammonia yield starts to decline as a consequence of the exothermic nature of the reaction. Beyond this regime, further temperature increases lead to lower equilibrium conversions, so that thermodynamic constraints dominate and the observable rate no longer increases monotonically with temperature. Because the overall reaction proceeds with a net decrease in the number of gas moles, increasing the total pressure shifts the equilibrium toward ammonia according to Le Chatelier's principle. This trend is clearly visible in Fig. 10 (a) (WHSV = 2862 mLn g_{cat}⁻¹ h⁻¹), at intermediate residence times, where higher pressure consistently enhances ammonia production. At high residence times, (Fig. 10 (b) (WHSV = 715 mLn g_{cat}⁻¹ h⁻¹)), however, the reactor approaches thermodynamic equilibrium, and the benefit of increasing pressure from 30 to 40 bar becomes marginal or can even reverse for some temperatures, except at the highest temperature investigated (450 °C). This complex behaviour arises from the interplay between thermodynamic limitations and kinetic effects, including ammonia inhibition [54]. As temperature increases, the equilibrium constant decreases for this exothermic reaction, shifting equilibrium away from NH₃ and making high pressure increasingly important to compensate for the loss in equilibrium yield. At the same time, higher temperatures accelerate the intrinsic kinetics and reduce the inhibitory effect of

adsorbed ammonia on the catalyst, so that the system can benefit more from additional pressure driving the equilibrium toward product formation.

3.3.2. Effect of H₂:N₂ molar feed ratio

To elucidate the influence of the hydrogen-to-nitrogen molar ratio on ammonia synthesis over the structured Ru-based catalyst, catalytic tests were performed at 40 bar varying the H₂: N₂ ratio between 2:1 and the conventional stoichiometric value of 3:1. Prior studies have shown that deviations from the stoichiometric feed composition can markedly impact ammonia productivity and overall catalyst utilization efficiency, particularly for ruthenium catalysts that are prone to hydrogen poisoning under hydrogen-rich conditions [55], [56], [57]. In line with these findings, Fig. 11(a–b) indicate that, across the investigated temperature range of 250–450 °C, the under-stoichiometric feed (H₂:N₂ = 2:1) generally delivers higher ammonia production rates than the stoichiometric feed, with the notable exception of 400 °C where the 3:1 ratio becomes slightly more favourable. This non-monotonic behaviour suggests a temperature-dependent balance between surface kinetics, hydrogen surface coverage, and thermodynamic constraints. For almost all temperatures, the lower H₂ partial pressure in the 2:1 feed likely mitigates hydrogen poisoning on Ru sites, enhancing N₂ activation and thus increasing the intrinsic reaction rate and effective catalyst productivity, despite the nominal hydrogen deficiency. Around 400 °C, however, the combination of accelerated surface kinetics and stronger equilibrium driving force at higher hydrogen partial pressure appears to outweigh the poisoning penalty, so that the stoichiometric 3:1 feed marginally outperforms the under-stoichiometric case, which is also in line with literature [58]. Hydrogen conversion increases with temperature for both feed compositions (Fig. 11(c–d)), and the H₂: N₂ = 2:1 case consistently exhibits higher H₂ conversion than the 3:1 case, indicating that hydrogen is more completely utilized under under-stoichiometric conditions. This reflects the complex interplay between reaction kinetics (enhanced at higher temperature and lower hydrogen coverage), equilibrium limitations (more severe at 2:1 when

Fig. 10. NH₃ production rate using inlet molar feed ratios H₂:N₂ = 2:1 as a function of temperature and pressure: (a) WHSV = 2862 mLn g_{cat}⁻¹ h⁻¹, (b) WHSV = 715 mLn g_{cat}⁻¹ h⁻¹.

Fig. 11. H₂:N₂ feed ratio investigation at WHSV = 2862 mLn g_{cat}⁻¹ h⁻¹: NH₃ production rate in function of (a) Temperature at 40 bar (b) Pressure at 450 °C, H₂ conversion in function of (c) Temperature at 40 bar (d) Pressure at 450 °C.

approaching high NH₃ yields), and reactor operation (fixed pressure and residence time). In a kinetic regime the reaction rate rises with the temperature especially since all available hydrogen is consumed quickly [59]. At the same time the reason of the non-monotonic behaviour of the ammonia production rate is that at 2:1, the system is much more sensitive to equilibrium limitations because there is less excess hydrogen to drive the reaction forward.

3.3.3. Effect of the WHSV

In addition to varying the H₂:N₂ feed ratio, the influence of Weight Hourly Space Velocity (WHSV) on ammonia synthesis was systematically investigated. WHSV is a critical operating parameter that governs the relationship between the molar feed rate, reactant conversion, and ammonia production rate. The aim is to identify the optimal operating regimes suitable also for the membrane reactor system investigation. The WHSV was varied in the range of 715–14273 mLn g_{cat}⁻¹ h⁻¹ by adjusting the total flow rate of the reactants between 150 and 3000 mLn min⁻¹, along with changes in pressure and temperature. Fig. 12 presents the results at 450 °C. Increasing WHSV led to a pronounced

enhancement in ammonia production rate, particularly at higher pressures, due to the higher reactant throughput. However, as the WHSV increased, the hydrogen conversion decreased, reflecting the reduced contact time between the gas phase and the catalyst surface. To ensure higher overall conversion, and allow for a reliable assessment of intrinsic catalytic performance as well as efficient ammonia permeation through the membrane [60], a low WHSV was selected for the membrane reactor experiments.

3.4. Performances of the structured catalyst membrane reactor

The performance of the Structured Catalyst-based Membrane Reactor (SCMR) was systematically investigated to evaluate its potential for enhanced ammonia synthesis compared to the conventional Structured Catalyst Reactor (SCR). In the following section, key reactor performance indicators, including ammonia recovery, yield, production rate, and hydrogen conversion, were analyzed as functions of temperature, pressure, weight hourly space velocity (WHSV), and sweep gas to feed flow ratio (SW). Comparative analysis with the conventional

Fig. 12. (a) NH₃ production rate (b) H₂ conversion as a function of WHSV at different pressures at 450 °C, H₂:N₂ = 2:1.

reactor was conducted using the improvement percentage defined in Eq. (10) to quantify performance enhancement under varying reaction conditions. It should be noted that the catalyst is located on the retentate side of the membrane in all cases. Furthermore, the same catalyst amount and identical WHSV were used in both configurations to ensure a fair comparison. Effect of the Temperature, Pressure and SW ratio.

The effect of the sweep gas to feed flow ratio (SW) on ammonia synthesis performance was systematically investigated using the structured catalyst-based membrane reactor (SCMR). The SW ratio, defined as the ratio of sweep gas flow to the feed gas flow, is a critical parameter governing the partial pressure gradient across the membrane and thereby influencing the reaction equilibrium. In our previous study [53] the significance of SW in enhancing overall conversion and ammonia production rate was demonstrated.

In this specific experimental investigation the sweep gas composition was selected to match that of the feed gas, corresponding to a molar feed ratio $H_2:N_2$ of 2:1. Furthermore, to facilitate a direct comparison between operating conditions, the pressure difference across the membrane (ΔP) was maintained at zero, ensuring equal pressure in both the retentate and permeate sides. This section evaluates the effect of varying SW ratios on hydrogen conversion, ammonia production rate, yield and recovery.

The effect of temperature on ammonia productivity in the structured catalyst membrane reactor is highly sensitive to the sweep gas to feed flow ratio (SW). As illustrated in Fig. 13(a–b) at low temperatures (250–300 °C) and for SW = 1–4, the membrane configuration offers no advantage and may even slightly reduce ammonia productivity compared to the conventional case, particularly at SW = 1. Under these conditions, the reaction is primarily governed by intrinsic kinetics, rendering the membrane-imposed driving force inadequate to overcome the intrinsically slow reaction rate; additionally, the introduction of sweep gas dilutes reactants at the membrane interface, further hindering the limited rate of ammonia formation. At the highest pressure examined (40 bar), this is compounded by hydrogen losses on the retentate side, which are particularly severe at SW = 1, where approximately 91 % of the hydrogen is removed from the retentate, compared with only

about 13 % at SW = 4 as shown in Fig. 14. In Fig. 13 (a), this detrimental effect is marginally more pronounced, although still barely perceptible, because the small amount of ammonia formed is more difficult to continuously remove. As the temperature increases, the intrinsic reaction rate becomes higher and the process enters a regime where both kinetics and equilibrium effects become competitive, making the membrane-assisted configuration more effective.

As the temperature increases, the intrinsic reaction rate rises and the system progressively enters a regime in which kinetic and equilibrium limitations become comparable, thereby enhancing the effectiveness of the membrane-assisted configuration. In this higher temperature window, the positive impact of in situ ammonia removal becomes more pronounced, and the performance gap between SW = 1 and SW = 4 widens, with larger sweep ratios enabling substantially higher ammonia production rates. At 350 °C and 30 bar, a sweep ratio of SW = 4 leads to a clearly measurable improvement in ammonia production rate of approximately 17 %, whereas the corresponding gain at SW = 1 is negligible, as shown in Fig. 13 (d). As further evidence of the thermodynamic benefits of the membrane-assisted configuration, the effect of sweep ratio at 40 bar clearly highlights a shift of the equilibrium limitation toward higher temperatures. In contrast to the conventional reactor (Fig. 10), where thermodynamic constraints already depress ammonia productivity at 400 °C and 40 bar, the membrane reactor delays this limitation to higher temperature, with the onset of pronounced equilibrium effects appearing only around 450 °C for SW = 1. At 450 °C and 30 bar, a sweep ratio of SW = 4 enables the membrane reactor to surpass the equilibrium conversion of the conventional configuration, achieving an improvement of approximately 94%. This behaviour is further clarified in Fig. 15 (a) which compares hydrogen conversion in the conventional and membrane-based reactors and places these results in the context of the corresponding thermodynamic equilibrium conversion. However at lower temperature, the hydrogen conversion of the conventional system remains higher than the membrane reactor, due to the huge amount of hydrogen back permeating, shown in Fig. 14 (a). At 450 °C, raising the pressure to 40 bar leads to a clear performance gap, with improvements of about 2.9 % at 400 °C and 7.2

Fig. 13. NH_3 production rate in the structured membrane reactor vs. conventional reactor at 250–450 °C at different pressure for (a) SW = 1, (b) SW = 4, (c) SW = 10, (d) comparison at 30–40 bar for different SW at 350 °C.

Fig. 14. H₂ trans-membrane flow at different temperatures: (a) 30 bar, SW = 1-4, (b) 40 bar, SW = 1-4-10.

Fig. 15. H₂ conversion for SW = 4 at different temperature at (a) 30 bar, (b) 40 bar for the SCMR and SCR compared to the thermodynamic equilibrium.

% at 450 °C relative to the conventional case. Fig. 15 (b) also illustrates the practical benefit of this shift: for a given conversion target, the membrane-based process can operate at significantly lower temperature than the conventional reactor. Specifically, the hydrogen conversion attained at 400 °C in the conventional configuration can already be reached at 300 °C in the membrane reactor.

For a more detailed assessment, additional experiments were carried out at SW = 10 and 40 bar (Fig. 13 (c)) to enable a clearer comparison with lower sweep ratios. Under these conditions, it becomes evident that even in the kinetically controlled regime at low temperatures (250–300 °C), the membrane reactor already outperforms the conventional reactor, showing that more intense in situ ammonia removal can partially offset the limitations imposed by slow intrinsic kinetics.

At 400 °C, however, Fig. 16 (b) reveals that SW = 10 yields lower performance than SW = 4; in this regime the system operates closer to thermodynamic equilibrium, and an excessively high sweep flow shortens the effective contact time thereby reducing the efficiency of ammonia extraction from the retentate and diminishing the overall benefit of the membrane configuration.

Table 2

Improvement on H₂ conversion, NH₃ production rate, NH₃ yield compared to the conventional process at 400–450 °C, 40–30 bar for SW = 1–4–10.

T [°C]	P [bar]	SW [-]	x _{H₂} [%]	NH ₃ production rate [%]	Y _{NH₃} [%]
400	40	1	113.7	52.6	38.8
400	40	4	83.3	76.8	53.4
400	40	10	32.3	63.4	61.2
450	40	1	7.1	70.7	77.8
450	40	4	7.35	131.5	123.4
450	40	10	-70.3	162.5	148.6
400	30	1	80.1	36.4	23.7
400	30	4	-79	41.7	46.1
450	30	1	16.3	248.4	120.7
450	30	4	94.7	133	7.9

In Table 2 there is an overview of the SCMR improvement, if any, respect to SCR in terms of NH₃ production rate, H₂ conversion and NH₃ yield.

Increasing the temperature amplifies the beneficial effect of the membrane reactor on ammonia productivity. Upon further increasing the temperature (450 °C), the positive impact of the membrane reactor on ammonia productivity becomes more pronounced. At 40 bar, the performance differences between SW = 1, SW = 4 and SW = 10 become markedly clearer, and Fig. 16 (b) shows that the combination of 40 bar and 450 °C delivers the highest total productivity. Under these conditions, the membrane reactor attains an ammonia production rate of 5.81 mmol g_{cat}⁻¹ h⁻¹ at SW = 10, compared to 2.21 mmol g_{cat}⁻¹ h⁻¹ in the conventional reactor, corresponding to a 162 % increase in NH₃ production rate, with an ammonia recovery factor of 84 %.

At 40 bar, the recovery factor remains comparatively high across the investigated temperature range (Fig. 16 (b)), although it gradually decreases with increasing SW, reflecting the combined effect of higher ammonia production rates and a reduced effective residence time for permeation. Conversely, at 30 bar (Fig. 16 (a)) the recovery factor declines more sharply with temperature for both sweep-gas conditions, indicating that, although the overall ammonia productivity is still competitive, separation on the permeate side is less effective than at 40 bar. This behaviour highlights that, at lower pressure, the driving force for ammonia transport through the membrane is insufficient to sustain efficient separation of the produced ammonia.

In other words, at 30 bar the membrane configuration maximizes productivity, whereas at 40 bar it favours ammonia recovery and separation performance.

3.4.1. Effect of WHSV

The influence of WHSV is particularly relevant in membrane-assisted configurations, where separation performance depends on sufficient residence time for permeation. At high flow rates, the overall production

Fig. 16. Total NH_3 production rate in the structured catalyst membrane reactor (SCMR) vs. recovery factor in the permeate at 250–450 °C (a) 30 bar, SW = 1–4, (b) 40 bar, SW = 1–10.

rate can increase, but the shortened residence time may hinder effective product removal through the membrane, limiting the intensification potential of the system. Therefore, an additional set of experiments was performed at higher WHSV, maintaining a sweep ratio of SW = 4 and a total pressure of 40 bar, and the results were compared with those obtained at lower WHSV, shown in Fig. 17.

In the investigated temperature range of 250–400 °C, the conventional reactor consistently exhibited higher productivity than the membrane integrated system at elevated WHSV, indicating that the benefit of product removal does not compensate for the kinetic and separation limitations under these conditions. At 450 °C the membrane reactor becomes competitive, achieving an increase in ammonia production rate of approximately 15 % relative to the conventional configuration. In this case the ammonia recovered in the permeate side was around the 87 % of the total produced amount.

4. Conclusions

This work demonstrates that a structured Ru-based catalyst integrated into a membrane reactor can significantly enhance ammonia synthesis performance over a wide range of operating conditions. The Ru-based catalyst was successfully coated as a uniform catalytic layer onto an open-cellular 3D support, and its behaviour was first characterized in a structured catalyst reactor, assessing the effects of temperature, pressure, $\text{H}_2:\text{N}_2$ molar feed ratio, and feed flow rate. Under these conventional conditions, an under-stoichiometric feed ratio of $\text{H}_2:\text{N}_2 = 2:1$ almost always outperformed the traditional stoichiometric ratio of 3:1, reflecting the well-known susceptibility of Ru catalysts inhibition

because of hydrogen and the beneficial effect of reducing hydrogen partial pressure on intrinsic activity.

In the membrane reactor, the sweep ratio emerges as the key design variable governing the trade-off between reaction enhancement and hydrogen losses. A moderate sweep ratio (SW = 4) provides the most favourable balance between reaction and separation, enabling operation beyond the conventional thermodynamic equilibrium limit, with hydrogen conversion exceeding equilibrium by ~15–30 % at 450 °C and 40 bar. Under near optimal conditions (400 °C, 40 bar), SW = 4 delivers simultaneous improvements of 83.38 % in H_2 conversion, 76.85 % in NH_3 production rate, and 53.40 % in NH_3 yield compared to a conventional reactor. In the low-temperature regime (250–300 °C, 40 bar), a higher sweep ratio (SW = 10) enhances NH_3 production rates by 25–43 % and yields by 15–19 %. At more severe conditions (450 °C, 40 bar), SW = 10 maximizes absolute productivity, reaching $5.81 \text{ mmol g}_{\text{cat}}^{-1} \text{ h}^{-1}$ and achieving up to 162 % higher NH_3 production rates and 148 % higher yields; however, it does not significantly promote equilibrium shifting. In contrast, at the same conditions, lower sweep ratios (SW = 1–4) yield production rate improvements of approximately 60–131 % while also enhancing conversion beyond equilibrium. These benefits, however, come at the expense of increased hydrogen permeation losses, particularly at low temperatures.

The influence of residence time, assessed via WHSV variation at SW = 4, shows that lower WHSV (i.e., longer residence time) improves performance by facilitating more effective in situ NH_3 removal. Notably, at 450 °C, the membrane reactor continues to outperform the conventional configuration even at higher WHSV, achieving ~28 % higher NH_3 productivity and an NH_3 recovery factor of 77 %. Overall, the results identify an optimal operating window characterized by high pressure (30–40 bar), moderate temperature (~400 °C), a moderate sweep ratio (SW = 4), and sufficiently low WHSV. This combination provides a robust compromise between kinetic enhancement, equilibrium shifting, and hydrogen utilization. In contrast, very high sweep ratios (SW = 10) are more suitable for applications prioritizing maximum NH_3 throughput over conversion efficiency and yield.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

I. Gargiulo: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Investigation, Conceptualization. **A. Vita:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Conceptualization. **C. Italiano:** Writing – original draft, Investigation, Conceptualization. **M.A. Llosa Tanco:** Writing – original draft, Investigation. **D.A. Pacheco Tanaka:** Writing – original draft, Investigation. **F. Gallucci:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial

Fig. 17. NH_3 production rate in a structured catalyst membrane reactor (SCMR) vs. structured catalyst reactor (SCR) at 40 bar, 250–450 °C, SW = 4 and different WHSV.

interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

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